

MEDICAL SCIENCES

QUALITY OF NURSING WORK LIFE IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

Assessing nurses' quality of work life helps predict nurse turnover, can increase organizational commitment, increase performance outcomes, and improve the quality of nursing health care. In hospitals, the quality of working life can make a positive contribution to medical institutions, medical staff and patients.

The purpose of this study was to determine the quality of work life of nurses employed in active care hospitals using Brooks' Quality of Nursing Work Life Survey. The reliability of the questionnaire in this study population showed a high internal consistency coefficient with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.89, and Cronbach's alpha values above 0.58 for each subscale.

In June-July 2022, a cross-sectional study was conducted among 821 nurses in 18 hospitals for active treatment, located in the territory of the city of Plovdiv and the Plovdiv region. With the highest relative share is the group of people working in multi-specialty hospitals (98.8%), almost evenly distributed between state (40.6%) and private (42.3%) hospitals.

The results showed that the overall mean QNWL score was 180.41 ± 24.06 . This accounts for a moderate quality of nursing work life. In three of the subscales (work life/home life, work context and work world) quality of nursing work life is at a moderate level, and in the work design subscale – high.

Understanding the quality of nursing work life will help manage the impact of such public health challenges as health worker motivation, satisfaction, attraction and retention.

Keywords: Quality of Working Life, Nurses, Quality of Nursing Work Life Survey, Work Design, work life-home life, work context, work world.

Introduction

Nursing shortages and turnover are major challenges for many healthcare systems and are related to the quality of work life (QWL) of employees. The quality of the professional life of healthcare providers is an important issue because it directly affects the quality of patient care [10]. Better QWL attracts and retains qualified staff, improves the quality and safety of nursing care, and increases organizational productivity and efficiency.

QWL is a multidimensional construct that began to be used in the 1970s and is related to motivation, job satisfaction, commitment to the organization and factors such as work commitment, occupational safety, ability enhancement, work-life balance personal life, work efficiency [3, 17].

Closely related to the concept of quality of work life is the quality of nursing work life Quality of nursing work life (QNWL) [11, 12]. It was developed on the basis of the quality of professional life and is used in research related to nursing [17].

Brooks et al. [5, 6, 7] defined QNWL as the extent to which nurses are able to satisfy important personal needs through their experience in the work organization while achieving organizational goals.

Like the QWL and QNWL constructs, it is related to sociotechnical systems theory, and assessments of nurses' quality of work life focus on identifying opportunities for nurses to improve their work and work environment while achieving organizational goals. Additionally, Brooks et al. [7] suggest that improvements are needed in professional life, namely that QNWL assessment reveals those areas for improvement where the needs of nurses and the organization intersect.

Identifying the factors that can influence QNWL can help managers to increase productivity and improve the quality of care in healthcare facilities. Improving QWL is a comprehensive process and is essential for attracting and retaining staff [14].

Public health challenges affect the motivation, retention of staff in health facilities. Understanding the quality of their working life will shed light on managing the impact of these challenges [15].

Therefore, it is not surprising that much research has been conducted specifically on concepts related to the quality of nurses' professional life.

Aim

To determine the quality of work life of nurses employed in active care hospitals using the Brooks' Quality of Nursing Work Life Survey.

Material and methods

A cross-sectional survey was conducted in June-July 2022. A socio-demographic questionnaire and the Brooks' Quality of Nursing Work Life Survey (BQNWL) were used. The questionnaire is for self-completion [4]. It consists of 42 items divided into 4 subscales: work life/home life, work context, work design and work world. Each of the scale items requires a response based on a six-point Likert scale ranging from 1; strongly disagree to 6; strongly agree. The total possible score for the Brooks scale can range from 42 to 252. Scores are obtained by summing and averaging the items. Depending on the results, QNWL is grouped into three levels – low, moderate and high [6].

The authors suggest that scale scores can be classified into two groups according to the respondent's level of agreement; that is, positive "agree" responses (4, 5, or 6) as "agree" and negative "disagree" responses (1, 2, or 3) as "disagree." Respondents who chose 1 to 3 on the scale were considered dissatisfied with the item, while those who chose 4 to 6 on the scale were considered satisfied with the item [6, 7].

The QNWL questionnaire has been shown to be a valid and reliable instrument for measuring different aspects of nurses' professional life. According to Brooks, the test-retest reliability of the QNWL was Pearson's $r = 0.90$ ($N = 53$), and Cronbach's alpha values were above 0.55 for each subscale. In terms of construct validity, the total calculated for the 42-item

survey using Cronbach's alpha was 0.89 ($N = 265$). The questionnaire is graded at level seven using the Flesch-Kincaid formula and requires 9-13 minutes to complete [4, 5].

Brooks' Quality of Nursing Work Life Survey was used by Prodanova and Kundurzhiev [13]. After receiving written permission, they validated the Brooks Quality of Work Life Assessment Tool in Bulgaria. Their pilot testing was among 21 nurses. After 30 days, a retest was done. The results obtained by Prodanova and Kundurzhiev show high internal consistency ($\alpha=0.863$). Test-retest reliability was assessed by intraclass correlation coefficient ($ICC=0.980$). Construct validity was assessed by factor analysis. Bartlett's test of sphericity showed significance ($p<0.05$) in each of the four subscales, viz. there is at least one common factor that can be extracted. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy for the individual subscales was between 0.65 and 0.80. In the opinion of the authors, the QNWL scale is sufficiently reliable and valid and can be used as an instrument in Bulgaria.

Brooks' Quality of Nursing Work Life Survey, translated and validated by Prodanova and Kundurzhiev [13], was used in this study.

Reliability analysis of the BQNWL questionnaire in this study population showed a high internal consistency coefficient with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.89, and Cronbach's alpha values were above 0.58 for each subscale.

	Cronbach's Alpha
Total score	0.892
work life/home life	0.595
work context	0.582
work design	0.889
work world	0.594

The required sample for this study was estimated as $n = 342$. Data collection was carried out over a period of six weeks from June to July 2022 on the territory of 18 hospitals for active treatment located in the territory of the city of Plovdiv and the Plovdiv region. The questionnaire was completed by 821 respondents.

Statistical methods

Descriptive statistical tests were used. Quantitative variables are represented by summarizing statistical characteristics - arithmetic mean (Mean), median

(Median), standard deviation (SD). Categorical variables are presented by absolute frequencies (n) and relative frequencies (%). In statistical processing of the data we used SPSS version 20.

Results

Sample profile

The distributions of respondents by main socio-demographic characteristics are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Distribution of respondents by main demographic characteristics			
Variable	Categories	N	%
Gender	Male	19	2.3
	Female	802	97.7
Age	< 25	47	5.7
	25-34	101	12.3
	35-44	173	21.1
	45-54	289	35.2
	55-64	139	16.9
	≥ 65	72	8.8
Highest level of education	Bachelor	517	63.0
	Professional Bachelor	121	14.7
	Master's degree	182	22.2
	PhD	1	0.1
Marital status	Married (first marriage)	441	53.7
	Married (not first marriage)	19	2.3
	Cohabitation without marriage	104	12.7
	Separated	13	1.6
	Divorced	67	8.2
	Unmarried	133	16.2
	Widower/Widow	44	5.4
Ethnic group	Bulgarian	774	94.3
	Turkish	34	4.1
	Romani	1	0.1
	Armenian	5	0.6
	Jewish	1	0.1
	Other	6	0.7
Living with children	Children up to 5 years	63	7.7
	Children from 6 to 18 years.	233	28.4
	Children over 18	264	32.1
Caring for an unemployed husband/wife	Yes	52	6.3
	No	769	93.7
Caring for parents	Yes	331	40.3
	No	490	59.7

Description of job related characteristics

The distribution by categories of the variables: type of ownership of the medical facility, type of activity and settlement (territorial location of the hospital) reveals that the group of workers in multi-specialty hospitals (98.8%), almost evenly distributed,

has the highest relative share between state (40.6%) and private (42.3%) medical facilities located on the territory of a regional city (87.3%).

Summary statistical characteristics of the demographic variables age and work experience are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Summary statistical characteristics of the demographic variables age and work experience						
Variable	N	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
Age	821	46.62	47.00	12.45	22.00	83.00
Years of total work experience	821	23.91	24.00	12.91	0.40	52.00
Years of experience as a nurse	821	22.52	22.00	13.22	0.16	52.00
Years of experience in the current medical facility	821	13.29	10.00	12.31	0.08	50.00
Years of experience in the current position (position)	821	12.37	9.00	11.87	0.08	50.00

The distribution of employment-related variables shows that 790 (96.2%) are on a main employment contract; 759 (92.4%) are full-time; 730 (88.9%) are in the position of "nurse"; 82.1% do not have a specialty certificate; just over half of all respondents (50.7%) also worked in Covid-19 wards during the 2020-2022 pandemic. 15.2% of respondents were found to be working pensioners.

Quality of nursing work life of nurses

Tables 3 and 4 present the QNWL of the nurses in the study. The overall mean QNWL score was 180.41 ± 24.06 . This accounts for a moderate quality of nursing work life. The QNWL scale has four dimensions. In three of these areas QNWL scored moderately and in one it scored high.

Table 3.

Summary statistics of QNWL results.						
Scale	N	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
QNWL total score	821	180.41	182.00	24.06	105.00	239.00
work life/home life	821	27.96	28.00	5.16	7.00	42.00
work context	821	40.81	41.00	6.27	14.00	60.00
work design	821	93.05	94.00	14.03	43.00	120.00
work world	821	18.58	19.00	3.66	6.00	30.00

Table 4.

Overall score and work life quality subscales	
Scale	Result
QNWL total score	moderate QNWL
work life/home life	moderate QNWL
work context	moderate QNWL
work design	high QNWL
work world	moderate QNWL

With the highest relative share in the total scale and three of the subscales are the respondents with a moderate level of quality. An exception is the Work Environment subscale, in which no nurses with a low level of QNWL are observed, but with the highest

relative share of individuals with a high level of quality.

Only 1.1% of the respondents had a low overall level of QNWL, 50.7% - a moderate level of QNWL and 48.2% - a high level of QNWL (Table 5).

Table 5.

Distribution of respondents by QNWL levels		N	%
Total QNWL	Low	9	1.1
	Moderate	416	50.7
	High	396	48.2
	Total	821	100.0
Work life/home life	Low	33	4.0
	Moderate	470	57.2
	High	318	38.7
	Total	821	100.0
Work context	Low	15	1.8
	Moderate	574	69.9
	High	232	28.3
	Total	821	100.0
Work design	Moderate	110	13.4
	High	711	86.6
	Total	821	100.0
Work world	Low	37	4.5
	Moderate	554	67.5
	High	230	28.0
	Total	821	100.0

Discussion

In this study, the overall mean QNWL score was 180.41 ± 24.06 . Although this accounted for a moderate quality of nursing work life in 50.7% of respondents, almost as many (48.2%) of nurses had a high level of QNWL.

A systematic review by Viselita et al. [18] for studies from eight countries revealed that the level of QNWL was low (28.6%), moderate (52.4%) and high (19%) of the studies.

Moderate QNWL scores have been reported in a number of studies in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, Iran, Jordan, and Ethiopia among nurses working in various healthcare settings [1, 8, 9, 16].

The finding of this study is consistent with previous reports and shows that, regardless of research location and work, the highest relative proportion are nurses with a moderate level of overall QWL in their jobs. The same conclusion was reached by Alreshidi & Alsharari [2].

Conclusion

In this study, we found a moderate quality of nursing work life. More than five out of ten of the nurses surveyed were not satisfied with the quality of their working life. Moderate level of QNWL in three of the subscales. An exception is the Work design subscale, for which a high level of QNWL was registered among more than 86% of nurses in the sample. The most critical is QNWL in the Work world subscale – there the relative share of individuals with a low (4.5%) level of QNWL is the largest, and the share of nurses with a high level of QNWL (28%) is the smallest.

The finding of this study adds little but essential information about the level of quality of work life among nurses in health care facilities in Bulgaria.

The results reported by other such studies show that nurses' perception of the quality of their work life can be changed in a positive direction if health care managers are aware of the key issues related to QWL [9].

Further future research may extend the scope of the present results and offer a more global understanding of nurses' quality of work life.

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